

Rare manuscripts stored in funds are rare masterpieces of the rich spirituality of our country

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Abstract: The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the system of preservation and research of ancient written sources" to restore our national-spiritual heritage and promote it internationally, our great scholars and thinkers ancestors Collecting, studying and studying thousands of rare works by foreign partners has opened the door of new opportunities for them to research. This article covers rare manuscripts, which are rare masterpieces of rich spirituality in our country.

Key words: Uzbekistan, unique, masterpieces, manuscripts, works, preservation.

Абстрактный: Решение Президента Республики Узбекистан «О дополнительных мерах по совершенствованию системы сохранения и исследования древних письменных источников» в целях восстановления нашего национально-духовного наследия и продвижения его на международном уровне, наших великих предков учёных и мыслителей Собираение, изучение и изучение тысячи редких работ зарубежных партнеров открыли перед ними новые возможности для исследований. В данной статье рассматриваются редкие рукописи, являющиеся редкими шедеврами богатой духовности в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, уникальность, шедевры, рукописи, произведения, сохранение.

In recent years, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturidi international scientific research centers, Center of Islamic civilization in Uzbekistan, International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan were established and are continuously functioning. Such auspicious events in our country are also gaining recognition from the international community. With the new decision, the scope of work in this regard will expand even more.

According to the decision, it is very important to create a state register of ancient written sources and integrate them into the activities of state-owned museum, library and archive funds. Until now, every scientific-research institution in our country has been working independently in a certain sense. If research is conducted in a centralized manner, there will be no room for parallel, repetitive work, cooperation and exchange of experience will be activated, and different institutions will enrich their manuscript funds with the help of each other.

The modern laboratory for the conservation and restoration of ancient written sources, which is being established at the Center of Islamic Civilization, certainly serves this good purpose. He is engaged in prevention of damage of ancient written sources under the influence of chemical, biological and other factors, preventive and stabilizing conservation and restoration, restoration and repair of volumes based on the traditions of calligraphy and cover-making.

Employees of other research institutions in our country can improve their skills and exchange experience here. Some organizations, in particular, the Imam Bukhari International Research Center, are actively working to collect manuscripts kept by our compatriots.

Of course, not all of these rare resources are in good condition. Some are in dire need of urgent professional restoration, followed by reliable conservation. Cooperation with this laboratory is very important in literally saving such resources and preserving them for future generations.

The necessary logical continuation of these considerations is clearly expressed in the decision. For example, at the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod, personnel are trained in the field of "Conservation and restoration of ancient written sources" (undergraduate). Because there are a lot of manuscripts to be given to the laboratory being established under the Center of Islamic Civilization, it should be constantly provided with personnel with strong knowledge and professional qualifications.

Another aspect is the educational process, practice, diploma thesis and master's theses defenses of students of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan in "Textual Studies and Literary Source Studies" and "Philology and Language Teaching (Classical Languages)" Institute, Center of Islamic Civilization, State Literature Museum and other manuscript funds with the participation of field scientists. After all, textual studies and source studies are directly related to written sources, and in order to study any manuscript, it is necessary to have a certain level of knowledge of Arabic, Persian languages, and ancient types of letters. The involvement of expert scientists in the process of protecting the educational and scientific work of new personnel allows to increase the level of their professional readiness. Graduates gather skills and experience in their field before starting work in the field. More specifically, he has a certain experience in the type and quality of paper, approach to them, types of writing and ink, and approaches work professionally. Therefore, the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan was designated as the main higher education institution in this direction.

Graduates of this academy should become skilled masters of their profession in the future. Because from now on, the fate of manuscripts - restoration, preservation or conservation, research and promotion will largely depend on how these personnel work. Therefore, the decision envisages the organization of internships in prestigious foreign museums, laboratories and archival funds for scientific workers and restorers engaged in the preservation and research of manuscripts. Essentially, the owners of this profession work with paper, paints and covers of different composition and quality, belonging to different periods. Some of them are widespread in Central Asia, while others are unique to this region.

Therefore, a special approach to the restoration, preservation, conservation, and research of each manuscript is necessary. To increase the knowledge, experience and skills of our national personnel in this regard, it is time to send them to foreign scientific institutions.

By organizing scientific expeditions to foreign countries, measures are taken to identify catalogs and electronic copies of ancient written sources on the work of scholars and thinkers of our country, translate them and put them into scientific circulation. This clause of the decision serves to enrich our national funds in every way. Of course, catalogs and electronic copies of some manuscripts are now being brought from foreign countries. In particular, catalogs and electronic copies of manuscripts related to the works of our scholars such as Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturidi were brought to the Imam Bukhari International Research Center from funds in countries such as Egypt, Great Britain, and Turkey. Now the scope of activity of all scientific and research institutions in our country will expand in this regard.

As noted in the document, in cooperation with prestigious international organizations and research institutions such as UNESCO, Islamic World

Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (ICESCO), Islamic History, Culture and Art Research Center (IRCICA) traditionally, international conferences dedicated to current issues of protection and research of ancient written sources are organized. In this way, it is possible to make copies of rare manuscripts that are not available in the funds of Uzbekistan, but are stored in the treasures of libraries abroad, and to enrich our national fund, to restore valuable manuscripts that have not been preserved according to the appropriate standards, together with foreign researchers and restorers, to research and widely presentation to the public, it will be possible to study and acquire international experience in working with manuscripts in general.

Within the framework of the Central Asian region, the issue of establishing cooperation relations with neighboring countries in the field of preservation and research of ancient written sources is also very urgent. After all, the peoples of the countries of our region keep many manuscripts in their personal, family, and dynastic funds. Identifying, copying and studying them not only activates scientific cooperation in the entire Central Asian region, but also expands the ranks of scientists in each country. There is no doubt that the resource that is not available in our neighborhood is very likely to be available in our neighborhood, which is not available in Uzbekistan. Considering this, regional cooperation plays a very important role in mutual exchange of knowledge and experience, strengthening of our joint skills.

According to the document, a scientific and educational portal about the life, scientific and spiritual heritage of scholars and thinkers of our country and its mobile application will be launched on the Internet. This will make it easier to convey the research of hundreds and thousands of our scientists to the general public, and it will

create opportunities for our compatriots and foreign science enthusiasts to get a lot of valuable information.

This decision of the President creates an opportunity to bring to the attention of our compatriots and foreign scientists the resources that our people have been unable to use for centuries due to various political and social factors. Thanks to this document, there is no doubt that thousands of unique manuscripts will be rediscovered.

References:

1. T. S. Saidkulov. Clips from the history of the peoples of Central Asia. - Tashkent: "Teacher". 1993. -B. 3-9.
2. Sobranie vostochnyx rukoposey Akademii nauk Respubliki Uzbekistan. History. Composable D. Yu. Yusupova, R.P. Djalilova. -Tashkent: "Fan". 1998. -S. 3-7.
3. Rukopisnaya kniga v kulturakh narodov Vostoka. Kniga pervaya.-Moscow: "Nauka". 1987.-S.5-17.
1. Аҳмедов Б.А. Ўзбекистон тарихи манбалари. – Тошкент. Ўқитувчи, 2001.
2. Аҳмедов Б.А. Историко-географическая литература. Средней Азии XVI-XVIII в. – Тошкент. Фан, 2001.
3. Муниров Қ. Хоразмда Тарихнавислик. –Тошкент. 2002.
4. Тарихий манбашунослик. Тузувчилар: А.А. Мадраимов, Г.С. Фузаилова. –Тошкент. Фан, 2006.
5. Манбашуносликдан маърузалар мажмуаси. Тузувчи А.А. Мадраимов. –Тошкент: 2001.
6. Ислом энциклопедияси. З.Хусниддинов тахрири остида. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон Миллий энциклопедияси, 2004.

7. Ўзбекистоннинг ислом цивилизациясига қўшган ҳиссаси. Масъул муҳаррирлар: Б.А.Абдуҳалимов, З.И.Мунаваров. –Тошкент, Самарқанд: 2007.
8. Беруний қадимги халқлардан қолган ёдгорликлар. –Тошкент: 1968.
9. Ртвеладзе Э.В. Великий шелковый путь. –Тошкент. 1999.
10. Ҳасаний М. Шарқ қўдёмаларини тавсифлаш ва фихристлаш. – Тошкент. 2004.